

GMJ.ge

Georgian Medical Journal

ISSN 3088-4322 (Online)

Commentary

Public Health Policy as Educational: Beyond Short-Term Behaviour Change in Non-Communicable Disease Prevention

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Georgian Medical Journal. 2026;1(1):8–13.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19046201>

Abstract

Public health policies to prevent non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are typically assessed through their short-term behavioural effects, yet their longer-term normative and educational influences are also key to consider. This commentary argues that public health policy should also be understood as a mechanism that shapes social norms, preferences, and autonomy over time. Recognising this guiding role is essential for a fuller evaluation of policy legitimacy and impact in contemporary NCD prevention.

Non-communicable disease (NCDs) prevention public health policies are evaluated primarily through their short to medium-term, observable outcomes, such as behavioural changes, rather than through their longer-term, system-wide health impacts. Standard evaluation frameworks distinguish these outcome measures from longer-term impacts, but in practice the latter are more difficult to attribute and are therefore less frequently assessed, particularly for large-scale policies affecting whole populations (1,2). Health taxes, smoking restrictions, or minimum pricing for alcohol are typically justified and assessed on the basis of the reductions in consumption that follow. While these outcomes are key, such an approach sometimes fails to account for a deeper and more enduring function of public health policy: its capacity to guide social norms, shape preferences, and contribute to long-term changes in beliefs about health, responsibility, and acceptable risk (3). This commentary argues that public health policies should be understood not merely as tools for short and mid-term behavioural correction, but as

normative and educational interventions that play a role in shaping the social meaning of health-related choices.

Public health evaluation frameworks have increasingly attempted to identify the most effective interventions for NCD prevention. The World Health Organization's "Best Buys" and related recommended interventions highlight highly cost-effective measures such as tobacco taxation, alcohol control policies, and restrictions on unhealthy food marketing. These measures are commonly evaluated through short-term indicators, including reductions in consumption and other observable behavioural changes. However, beyond these measurable effects, such interventions also perform an important signaling function. By embedding health norms within law and regulation, they help shape public expectations and the social meaning of health-related behaviour over time. Recognising this additional function helps position NCD prevention policy not only as a behavioural instrument, but also as a long-term normative and educational intervention.

This broader perspective is especially helpful in looking at the more controversial or restrictive policies, i.e., so-called "paternalistic" interventions, that limit the autonomy or free choice of individuals for their supposed interest (4). Critics sometimes object to public health interventions on the grounds they interfere with individual choice and treat adults as incapable of making health decisions. Such critiques assume that preferences are fixed, fully informed, and independent of social context. However, preferences are shaped by many external environmental factors, information, commercial practices, and social norms. Public health policy does not intervene in a neutral space; rather, it operates within environments already shaped by social norms, commercial actors, market strategies, and longstanding cultural practices. Recognising this guiding role of policy over time is important in thinking about their legitimacy.

From Incentives to Meaning: How Policies Signal Social Values

One way in which public health policies exert a guiding influence is through the signals they send about social values. When the State taxes tobacco, restricts advertising, or mandates plain packaging, it does more than make smoking more expensive or less convenient. It communicates that smoking is harmful, socially undesirable, and not an ordinary consumer good. Over time, these signals contribute to shifts in public attitudes, particularly among younger generations who grow up with these policies as part of the background conditions of everyday life.

This signalling function helps to explain why the impact of public health policies often extends beyond their immediate behavioural effects. For example, smoking prevalence in Western countries declined over the last decades (5, 6) not only because tobacco products became more expensive, but because smoking was increasingly stigmatised and denormalised. This denormalisation is the cumulative result of decades of policies: taxation, advertising bans, and public information campaigns, that together helped reshape how smoking is perceived. The policy environment educates citizens about risks, but also about what kinds of behaviour are socially endorsed or discouraged.

Similar dynamics can be observed in relation to drink-driving, seatbelt use, and dietary choices. Policies such as calorie labelling, sugar taxes, and restrictions on junk food marketing to children contribute to a broader narrative about responsibility for health (3). They help establish the idea that foods high in fat, salt, or sugar are not merely matters of individual taste but issues

of public concern. In this sense, public health policy participates in the construction of social meaning by influencing not only what people do, but also what they come to regard as reasonable, responsible, and socially acceptable behaviour.

Education, Autonomy, and the Long-Term Formation of Preferences

One common critique of such health policies is that they sometimes overly restrict individual autonomy in favour of health gains (7,8). Yet autonomy should not be understood solely in terms of unimpeded choice at one point in time. Rather, autonomy has a developmental dimension: it is dependent on individuals having the capacities, knowledge, and social conditions, e.g., valuable options, necessary to form and revise their preferences in light of relevant reasons (9). Public health policies can support this form of autonomy by contributing to an informational and normative environment that enables more reflective decision-making over the long term (3). Even the more “invasive” interventions like fiscal interventions or specific bans can have an educational effect, prompting individuals to reflect on why certain products are discouraged and to reassess their own consumption patterns. Over time, repeated exposure to these cues can lead to internalised changes in values, reducing reliance on external constraints. As noted by Arneson, *“restriction of choice now even to the extent of forcing a single choice upon the individual can pave the way to autonomous choice of that good or others later. This long-run fostering of autonomous choice of the good is easier to bring about if the coercion does not force upon the agent a single option thought to be good but instead prohibits some tempting bad options while leaving many other options open.”* (10)

This challenges the common objection that certain public health policies undermine autonomy by substituting state judgement for individual judgement. If policies contribute to the formation of better-informed and more health-conscious preferences, they may in fact enhance autonomy in a meaningful sense by improving the quality of decision-making environments. Few would argue, for example, that individuals who choose not to smoke today have become less autonomous as a result of decades of tobacco control policies. The fact that individuals increasingly choose to smoke less, consume fewer unhealthy foods, or demand healthier products reflects a shift in evaluative frameworks shaped through long-term social learning. In that sense, policies can help reduce the prevalence of NCDs through mechanisms that extend beyond immediate economic incentives such as price increases. Public health policy therefore operates not only at the level of choice architecture, but also at the deeper level of preference formation.

Demand, Markets, and the Co-Evolution of Policy and Behaviour

Understanding the guiding role of public health policy also has important implications for how we think about markets and demand. Consumption patterns are often interpreted as expressions of individual preferences to which markets simply respond (11). In reality, however, demand is shaped by a range of structural factors including regulation, advertising, product availability, and price structures. Public health policies intervene within this environment by altering incentives, information flows, and regulatory conditions that influence consumer behaviour. In doing so, policy does not merely respond to demand but also contributes to shaping what consumers come to expect, value, and ultimately demand within markets.

An additional dimension relevant to this discussion is the role of the commercial determinants of health. Industries producing unhealthy commodities such as tobacco, alcohol, and ultra-processed foods do not merely respond to consumer demand; they actively shape it through

marketing, product design, pricing strategies, distribution systems, and political lobbying. These commercial practices influence the informational and economic environments within which individuals form preferences and make choices. Recognising these commercial determinants is therefore essential to understanding why health-related preferences cannot be treated as independent of social context. Public health policy does not intervene in a neutral marketplace, but rather within markets already structured by actors whose interests may conflict with population health goals.

Public health policies intervene in this process, altering the incentives and information that shape consumer behaviour, but also influencing what consumers come to want. For example, sustained regulation of tobacco products has not only reduced smoking rates but has transformed the tobacco market itself. As demand declined in many countries, social acceptance has waned, and the industry's capacity to recruit new consumers has been curtailed. A similar process may be underway with respect to unhealthy food. Policies targeting sugar, salt, and fat content, combined with restrictions on marketing and labelling, can gradually shift consumer expectations. As healthier options become the norm rather than the exception, demand adjusts accordingly.

This dynamic highlights the importance of viewing public health policy as a long-term project rather than a series of isolated interventions. Undeniably, short-term behavioural changes matter, but significant effects are often only seen over decades, as policies reshape the social and economic environment in which choices are made. Evaluating policies solely on short and mid-term consumption effects risks undervaluing these cumulative and structural impacts.

Guidance Rather Than Control

Reframing public health policy as a long-term guiding and educational force allows for a more nuanced understanding of policies sometimes criticised as overly restrictive or “paternalistic”. Rather than presenting a simple opposition between coercion and freedom of choice, this perspective recognises that policies influence behaviour through a variety of mechanisms that include guidance, signalling, and social learning. Many public health interventions can therefore be understood as forms of guidance that steer behaviour while preserving space for reflection and choice. Even when policies impose certain restrictions, their justification may lie not only in preventing immediate harm but also in fostering healthier social environments in which individuals can develop more informed and reflective preferences over time.

This does not imply that all such policies are justified, nor that concerns about overreach should be dismissed. Questions about proportionality, effectiveness, and respect for plural values remain crucial (12). However, acknowledging the guiding role of policy helps clarify what is at stake. The relevant question is not simply whether a policy changes behaviour effectively, but what kind of social learning it promotes and how it contributes to the long-term distribution of health opportunities.

Table 1. Contrasting conventional short-term evaluation models with the long-term educational framework of public health policy

Dimension	Conventional evaluation model	Long-term educational framework
Main objective	Immediate behavioural change	Long-term shaping of preferences and norms
Main indicators	Consumption reduction, uptake, compliance	Social learning, denormalisation, expectation change
Time horizon	Short to medium term	Long term
View of policy	Instrument to change behaviour	Educational and normative force
View of autonomy	Risk of restricting individual choice	Potential support for reflective and informed autonomy
View of markets	Markets respond to existing preferences	Preferences and demand are shaped by policy and commercial forces
Main justification	Observable effect on behaviour	Structural influence on beliefs, norms, and health opportunities

This conceptual comparison illustrates how NCD prevention policy may be understood not only through short-term behavioural effects, but also through its long-term role in shaping norms, preferences, and health-related expectations.

Conclusion

Public health policies are more than instruments for short and mid-term behavioural change. They are powerful educational and normative tools that shape beliefs, preferences, and social norms over time. By guiding individuals towards healthier ways of thinking about risk, responsibility, and wellbeing, NCD prevention policies can reduce harmful demand, transform markets, and support a richer conception of autonomy. Recognising this guiding role helps us understand the integral function of public health intervention in addressing socially shaped preferences and collective health risks and is essential for a coherent and defensible public health ethics.

Acknowledgments

I kindly thank Dr Mark Sheehan and Dr Mike Rayner for their insights on this topic.

Funding

None.

Competing interests

None.

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